

Synthesis and biological activity of copper(II) mixed ligand complexes with α -(2-thienyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)nitron as the primary ligand

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The complexing ability of α -(2-thienyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)nitron (LH) has been investigated. Copper complexes of the type CuL_2 have been prepared, where $\text{L}_1\text{H} = \text{salicylaldehyde/salicylaldoxime/salicylaldehyde semicarbazone/salicylaldehyde phenylhydrazone/salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone/8-hydroxyquinoline/2-hydroxypyridine}$. The complexes possess two coordinated water molecules and have a distorted octahedral structure. The involvement of nitron nitrogen in bond formation apart from phenolic oxygen has been suggested. The antibacterial activities of these nitrons have also been studied.

The nitrons behave like *N*-oxides rather than oximes in their complex formation resulting in bond formation with nitron oxygen apart from phenolic oxygen, leading to a seven-membered chelate ring¹. However, on the basis of ESR spectral data, later it was proposed² that the nitron-nitrogen is involved in bonding similar to that of oxime group and not the nitron-oxygen, resulting in a six-membered chelate ring. Recent reports from our laboratory on metal complexes of the nitrons^{3,4} also suggest that nitron-nitrogen is involved during metal ligand bond formation. In continuation of our work on the synthesis and biological activity of α -(2-thienyl)-*N*-arylnitrons⁵, it was proposed to investigate its chelating ability with copper(II) ion and study their biological properties. It is pertinent to mention that the mixed complexes involving a related system, thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone have been recently reported from this laboratory⁶.

Results and Discussion

Copper(II) complexes of α -(2-thienyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxyphenyl)nitron (LH) of the types $\text{CuL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuL}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been prepared, where $\text{L}_1\text{H} = \text{salicylaldehyde (SalH)/salicylaldoxime (SalOH)/salicylaldehyde semicarbazone (SalscH)/salicylaldehyde phenylhydrazone (SalphH)/salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (SalTscH)/8-hydroxyquinoline (OxineH)/2-hydroxypyridine (2-pyoH)}$. All the complexes (Table 1) have been tested for their purity by TLC. These coloured complexes are insoluble in water, benzene and carbon tetrachloride, and moderately soluble in chloroform and acetonitrile. They exist as dihydrates as they lose two molecules of water above 150° which may be due to the fact that these water molecules are strongly held

in the complexes via coordination. The presence of water molecule in the complexes is also confirmed by the IR band around 3300–3500 cm^{-1} . The elemental analysis data are consistent with 1 : 2 metal ligand ratio for the complexes. The magnetic moment values (Table 1) suggest a distorted octahedral structure for these complexes. The electronic spectrum of the parent complexes shows a broad band around 400–425 nm corresponding to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g} \text{ } {}^2E_g$ in a D_{4h} environment. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band of the ligand (1561 cm^{-1}) shifted to higher wavenumbers in the complexes (1578–1646 cm^{-1}), indicating the involvement of nitron nitrogen in bond formation. This kind of observation was noted in hydroxyoxime complexes⁷. The N–O stretching frequency of the ligand (1188 cm^{-1}) also altered in the complexes (1100–1166 cm^{-1}), but the coordination via nitron oxygen is ruled out by ESR studies.

Table 1. Elemental analyses and magnetic moment data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % :		μ_{eff} B.M
		Found	(Calcd.)	
$\text{CuL}_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	11.75	(11.86)	1.81
$\text{CuL}(\text{Sal}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Green	14.50	(14.49)	1.84
$\text{CuL}(\text{Salo}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	13.88	(14.01)	1.82
$\text{CuL}(\text{Salph}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	11.95	(12.02)	1.82
$\text{CuL}(\text{Salsc}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	13.00	(12.82)	1.92
$\text{CuL}(\text{SalTsc}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	12.33	(12.42)	1.97
$\text{CuL}(\text{Oxine}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	13.52	(13.77)	1.86
$\text{CuL}(2\text{-pyo}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	Brown	15.00	(15.44)	1.89

*All complexes did not melt sharply, decomposing above 200°.

ESR spectra of four complexes $\text{CuL}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuL}(\text{Sal}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuL}(\text{Salo}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuL}(\text{Salph}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were

recorded in the solid state and in chloroform solution at RT (Table 2). In the solution spectra, N-shf structure is well resolved into five lines, in fourth and in the third Cu-hyperfine lines with N_1 value of 15 G. The g values are in agreement with CuN_2O_2 chromophore for the CuL_2 complex and the mode of bonding in the above complexes is established to be via nitrono nitrogen and phenolic oxygen.

Table 2. EPR spectral data of the complexes

Compd.	Solid			Solution	
	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	g_0	A_0 in 10^{-4} cm^{-1}
$\text{CuL}_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2.162	2.066	2.100	2.090	80
$\text{CuL}(\text{Sal}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	—	—	2.121	2.130	75
$\text{CuL}(\text{SalO}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2.166	2.054	2.090	2.100	86
$\text{CuL}(\text{SalpH}) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	2.178	2.058	2.100	2.104	84

The antibacterial activity of the Cu^{II} complexes was evaluated against *Klebsiella arogers*, *Proteus* species, *Pseudomonas* species, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi* by disc diffusion method using ceftazidime as standard. The preliminary result reveals that $\text{CuL}(\text{SalTsc}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuL}(\text{Salc}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuL}(\text{Oxine}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are active against some of the organisms.

Experimental

The metal content of the complexes was estimated by incinerating them to the oxides. The magnetic susceptibility was measured using solid samples on a Gouy type magnetic balance at room temperature (303–308 K). The electronic spectra (nujol/acetonitrile) were measured on a Shimadzu UV 160 spectrophotometer and ESR spectra on a Varian E4 X-band spectrometer.

Bis[α -(2-thienyl)-N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)nitronato]diaquocopper(II) : To a solution of α -(2-thienyl)-N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)nitrono⁵ (2.2 g, 10 mmol) in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1;

200 ml) was added a solution of copper acetate (1 g, 5 mmol) in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, 200 ml) and the solution was allowed to stand overnight. The resulting complex was washed with aqueous alcohol (1 : 1), dried in air and then under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Mixed ligand complexes : To a solution of the primary ligand α -(2-thienyl)-N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)nitrono (2.2 g, 10 mmol) and the secondary ligand (10 mmol) in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1; 400 ml), was added a solution of copper acetate (2 g, 10 mmol) in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1; 200 ml) and the solution was allowed to stand overnight. The resulting complex was washed with aqueous alcohol (1 : 1), dried in air and then under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

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